

Strategic implication of the global mobile phone industry: Analyzing COVID-19 impact from competitive viewpoint

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the present scenario of global mobile phone companies in context of strategy implementation. Here the author tries to show the competitive scenarios of mobile phone companies in current situation. At the same time here it is also shown how COVID-19 affects the industry and its growth. In this qualitative study that is based on secondary data, some strategic directions are discussed that are and can be applied for sustainability and growth. Based on the data shown from published papers and online sources and subsequent discussion based on these data, there is insignificant negative effect of COVID-19 on global mobile phone brands. The outcome of this study is useful for the industry policy maker, investor, user, and other stakeholders of global mobile phone industry to tackle present and future COVID-19 situation. Finally, some strategic approaches are discussed and appropriate solutions are suggested to cope up with the pandemic situation and attain success.

Keywords: COVID-19 impact, competitive approach, global mobile phone brand, strategic implication

Discussion on COVID-19 impact on mobile phone industry

COVID-19 has originated from Wuhan, China on 31st December 2019 and ongoing spread approximately 216 countries around the world (Usman et al., 2020; WHO, 2020). WHO (2020) reports in their website that there are 20.16 million confirmed infected cases where 0.74 million death cases globally. Among the infected countries, near 52% are from top 3 countries USA, Brazil and India. Again, around 42% have died from these three countries out of total deaths throughout the world. Other countries having high death rates are in Mexico, UK, Italy, France, Spain, and

Peru having higher than 20K measures. Worldwide, medicine specialists are struggling to invent vaccine to prevent this virus from almost the beginning of the pandemic situation but no success stories have not been heard. Kamal et al. (2020) and UN News (2020) report that this virus will not disappear and sustain for long lasting announced by WHO. Fortunately, the good news on 11th August, Russian president Vladimir Putin declared that his country approved a vaccine against corona virus. Although, there are controversy with this vaccine of its quick launch (The New York Times, 2020), this initiative must show smiles to billions of people all over the world and will work as motivation for other specialist to bring more effective vaccines in future.

Generally, mobile companies produce smartphone and featured phone. The global mobile phone industry has an increased sales growth. Although in 2017, worldwide smartphone declined 0.5% for the first time year-over-year. In that specified year, the total delivery of smartphone devices was 1.46 billion. According IDC forecasted that mobile phone companies may enjoy a 2.8% compound annual growth rate (CAGR) from 2017 to 2022 with 1.68 billion sales volumes in 2022 (IDC, 2018). But this CAGR assumption may not be proved correct and the reason for this variation is for COVID-19. How this issue can affect this industry, a simple analysis is shown in the following table:

Table 1: Market analysis based on annual sales revenue and profits of top listed global mobile phone companies based on pandemic situation

Sl. No.	Global Brand Name	Yearly Units Sold (Smartphone units in million)			Yearly sales revenue (USD in million)		Yearly net income (USD in million)		Market Share (%)		
		2018 Q4	2019 Q2	2020 Q1	2018	2019	2018	2019	April 2018	October 2019	July 2020
1	Samsung	69.8	76.3	58.6	209,163	197,690	38,049	18,652	30.76	31.49	30.95
2	Huawei	59.7	56.6	49.0	105,191	123,640	8,543	9,030	6.21	10.02	10.75
3	iPhone	65.9	36.5	40.0	265,595	260,174	59,531	55,256	19.23	22.09	24.82
4	Xiaomi	25.6	32.3	29.7	25,182	29,634	1,940	1,454	6.12	7.79	8.94
5	Oppo	31.3	30.6	22.3	60,000	60,000	1,400	1,400	3.97	4.10	4.69
6	Vivo	26.5	27.0	21.6	46,484	46,484	1,125	1,125	7.81	8.00	7.00

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7	Realme	-	5.0	7.2	-	-	-	-	0.00	2.00	2.00
8	LG	-	-	-	51,730	52,540	1,240	150	3.22	2.40	2.03
9	Lenovo	-	-	-	51,038	50,716	842	998	2.53	0.96	0.74
10	ZTE	-	-	-	12,311	13,063	1000	831	0.63	-	-
11	Alcatel-Lucent	-	-	-	553	779	38	-29	0.47	-	-
12	Others	115.8	92.8	66.6	-	-	-	-	19.05	10.97	8.08

Source: Apple annual report (2020), Counterpoint (2020), "Huawei annual report," (2019), Lenovo annual report, (2020), LG annual report (2019), MBA Skool Team (2020), Samsung annual report, (2020), Statcounter (n.d.), Statista, (n.d.), Xiaomi annual report, (2020), ZTE annual report (2019)

The above table shows that more than 80% in 2019, around 90% in 2019, more than 90% in 2020 global market share is occupied by top 11 global mobile phone brands. Other popular brands having market share of 1.3% Alcatel-Lucent, 2.68% by Motorola, 1.73% by Nokia, 1.15% by Sony Ericsson, 1.29% by BBK, 0.97% by HTC, 1.06% by Micromax, 1.09% by Asus, 1.96% by Mobicel, 0.28% by General Mobile, 0.44% by Google Pixels, 0.41% by Sony and so forth (Statista, n.d.). From the table, we can guess that between 2019 and 2020 there are some differences of performance among top giant mobile phone companies. Especially major differences are seen in between second quarter of 2019 and first quarter of 2020 in terms of units sold as a result it affects the revenue and profit earnings. As we know COVID-19 first infected in the end of last quarter of 2019 and spread worldwide quickly, the major differences are seen afterwards. This scenario illustrates the negative impact of COVID-19 on mobile phone companies. Although the real impact can be measured after the pandemic situation overcomes and the in-depth analysis will be conducted based on time series of data. But we can say that this effect is not as alarming in comparison with other industries as we see surrounding us many industries are badly affected due to COVID-19 such as manufacturing sector like ready-made garments, footwear, apparel, jewelry, accessories etc.; service sector like education, restaurant, tourism, transport, film and media etc.; bureaucratic relationship like export-import, expatriate where we can see some sectors like technology, treatment, medicine, e-learning, social media, working at home have been increased.

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